

16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	3) Compensating and recognising carers Many OECD countries provide financial support to carers through a 'carer allowance' and/or direct payments to those in need of care (or to carers based on an assessment of their needs). Both types of payments (allowance and direct payments) are available in NI and the rest of the UK.	-	-	-	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/information-and-services/money-matters/carers-allowance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Carers Allowance	y	
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	https://www.cibelfast.org/content/what-are-direct-payments	-	-	-	y	
16.02.18	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/information-and-services/money-matters/carers-allowance	http://www.assemblyresearchmatters.org/2017/06/07/supporting-carers-in-northern-ireland/	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/information-and-services/money-matters/carers-allowance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Carer's Allowance An introduction to Carer's Allowance Carer's Allowance - changes in circumstances Carer's Allowance - effect on other benefits and entitlements Carer's Allowance - how to claim	National	-	-	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/articles/introduction-carers-allowance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Carers Allowance	y	
16.02.18	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/articles/introduction-carers-allowance	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/information-and-services/money-matters/carers-allowance	https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/articles/introduction-carers-allowance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	ou may be eligible for Carer's Allowance if you are aged 16 or over and you spend at least 35 hours a week caring for someone who is ill or has a disability. The amount is £62.70 a week. The allowance can affect other benefits that you or the person you care for receive.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
16.02.18	https://www.cibelfast.org/content/what-are-direct-payments	http://www.assemblyresearchmatters.org/2017/06/07/supporting-carers-in-northern-ireland/	https://www.cibelfast.org/content/what-are-direct-payments	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	1: A Direct Payment is an amount of money that you may be able to get instead of traditional services from your local Health & Social Care Trust. It will enable you to arrange your support in a way that suits you best. You can get Direct Payments if You are over 16 or You are a parent/guardian of a child under 16 who may be eligible You are assessed by a Social Worker or Care Manager as needing personal social services You are willing and able to manage Direct Payments (with as much help as necessary) You need help with daily living tasks 2:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	Direct Payments are available to Disabled people Older people who require support People with enduring mental health issues	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Direct payments to over 16s?	-
16.02.18	young carers legislation northern ireland	Google Search	http://www.niassembly.gov.uk/globalassets/documents/raise/publications/2017-2022/2017/health/2417.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	MARCH 2016 : This paper looks at the provisions for supporting carers in law and policy across the UK; key issues for carers, with additional reference to wider EU work in this regard; and some particular examples of good practice in selected EU countries. It may be read in conjunction with RalSe briefing paper NIAR 44-17 (March 2017, Dr Raymond Russell).	National	Dr Jennifer Betts and Dr Janice Thompson	Wrote paper	-	-	-	-	1: SAVED Carers.Legislation, Policy and Practice Dr Jennifer Betts and Dr Janice Thompson 2: It may be read in conjunction with RalSe briefing paper NIAR 44-17 (March 2017, Dr Raymond Russell). EUROPEAN OVERVIEW	n
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	3.1.3 Young carers Prior to the Children and Families Act 2014 there were no legal provisions specific to young carers under 16 years of age.46 Section 96, amended the Children Act 1989, giving young carers the same right to an assessment as adult carers, to include the appropriateness of the child providing care in respect to their own needs. However, there is no national eligibility criteria in England for the provision of services for young carers and local authorities only have to 'consider' the assessment when deciding whether to provide support for young carers.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Children and Families Act 2014 England	-

16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	4.1 Legislation in Scotland The Carers (Scotland) Act passed on 4 February 2016 and will be commenced from 1st April 2017. Its key objective was the intention that carers and young carers should be consistently supported in order that, if they wish, they should be able to continue in their caring role. It is also the intention that young carers should be able to have a childhood that is similar to their peers who do not have a caring role.	-	-	-	-	-	-	Scotland	-
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	The Scotland Act 2016 provided for the devolution of Carer's Allowance to Scotland. The Scottish Government plans to increase Carer's Allowance to match the rate of Jobseeker's Allowance, increasing the weekly rate from £62.10 (£62.70 from 1st April 2017) to £73.10. All the main Scottish political parties support this increase, although the Scottish Green Party would increase it further to £93.15 a week. The aim is to compensate carers for the contribution they make to society. ⁶⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-	Scotland	-
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	It is estimated that there are 745,000 adult carers, and 44,000 young carers in Scotland, ⁶⁹ with the total value of unpaid care in Scotland estimated at £10.3 billion per annum. In common with the Carers Act 2014 in England, the Carers (Scotland) Act ⁷⁰ ('the Act') removes the requirement for the care a carer provides to be 'substantial' and 'regular'. The Act (parts 2-6): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Replaces the current carer's assessment with a new adult carer support plan (ACSP) and provides a young carer statement (YCS) for all young carers; 	-	-	-	-	-	-	Scotland	-
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	Also published for the period 2010 – 2015 was Getting it Right for Young Carers ⁷³ . believed to be the first strategy specifically for young carers in Europe.	-	-	-	-	-	-	Scotland	-
19.02.18	https://www.careersuk.org/help-and-advice/practical-support/getting-care-and-support/young-carers-and-carers-of-children-under-18	Google Search 'young carers legal provisions England'	https://www.careersuk.org/images/Factsheets/Factsheet_NI1020__Assessments_-_guide_to_getting_help.pdf	NGO	Carers Organisations	Carers NI : A guide to getting Assessments: including for 2: Guidance on the Carers and Direct Payments Act emphasises that child carers should be treated as children first and carers second. 3: young carers will be assessed on Children (NI) Order 1995 using a process called UNOCINI: Understanding the needs of children in Northern Ireland 4: 16 and 17 year olds may also be assessed under Children (NI) Order 1995 5: They may alternatively and at their request be assessed under the Carers and Direct Payments Act 2002, although guidance suggests that this will only 'rarely' be in the young carers' best interests'.	National	-	info@careersni.org	www.lgo.org.uk	?	Legal	-	n
19.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	The Carers and Direct Payments Act guidance states that 'Children should be supported to avoid them assuming responsibility for levels of caring that could impact on their health and wellbeing, education and development'.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19.02.18	RaiSe briefing paper NIAR 44-17 (March 2017, Dr Raymond Russell)	http://www.niassembly.gov.uk/globalassets/documents/raise/publications/2017-2022/2017/health/2417.pdf	http://www.niassembly.gov.uk/globalassets/documents/raise/publications/2017-2022/2017/health/2517.pdf	Government website (National)	Legal	1: This Briefing Note contains background information and statistics on Carers in Northern Ireland, and draws attention to the more pertinent issues facing this group at present 2: Fig 3.2 Carers by Age Band, Census 2011 4% 0-17 3: There are also a significant number of young carers (those aged under 18). For example, 6,700 young people (aged 0-17) provide between 1 and 19 hours of unpaid care per week, while a further 960 provide 20 – 49 hours, and 820 work for 50 hours or more 4	National	Dr Raymond Russell	-	Carers UK (2016) State of Caring 2016. Available at: http://www.careersuk.org/for-professionals/policy/policylibrary/task/download?file=policy_file&id=5637	-	-	-	-
19.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	As noted above, around 6,700 young people (aged 0-17) provide between 1 and 19 hours of unpaid care per week, while a further 960 provide 20 – 49 hours, and 820 work for 50 hours or more. Taken together, young carers account for 4 per cent of all carers in Northern Ireland.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

